

Thinking about datification in the context of training: current challenges

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Abstract: Datification is the process of transforming data, through analysis and reorganization, into information that can be modified in any area of knowledge or discipline, but the different technological disruptive changes with the "Information Era", which is currently being experienced, have focused professionals in Library and Information Sciences (LIS) on the most important resource to make information available to society. Therefore, this article reflects on the education of LIS professionals as the most important challenge for adapting to the endless opportunities that appear today: cloud computing services (IBM Cloud, Google Cloud Platform, Azure), machine learning, the semantic web, MOOCs, open science and open access, free access bibliographic databases, among others. In conclusion, the objective for LIS professionals is to analyze before collecting data, and this is achieved with education and not by a stroke of luck or by simply using a tool.

Keywords: datification, LIS, challenges, opportunities, computer science, education.

1. Introduction

Thinking about the challenges for the training of professionals in the Library and Information Sciences (LIS), means problematizing and making visible the place of data in this "Information Era" (Cf. Castells, 2009; De Souza-Silva et al., 2001; Echeverría, 2015; Shannon & Weaver, 1949). To illustrate this, it is enough to review some statistics, for example, on January 5, 2020 there were 4,437,215,927 users on the Internet, representing 54.6% of the world's population (InternetLiveStats.com, 2020). Approximately three billion searches, 500 million tweets, five billion GB of data were generated per day. 600 million blogs were opened and some 230 million records were counted in bibliographic databases produced by some 32 million authors (mainly scientific and/or academic articles) in 65 million journals (Cambia.org, 2020; InternetLiveStats.com, 2020; WebsiteHostingRating.com, 2020). This surprising information forces us to ask ourselves: What is happening with this multitude of data, what should be done, who benefits from it and how should it be managed?

This work reflects and outlines some arguments on the need for training professionals in the LIS domain, to question and analyze the use of data to be useful in any discipline and/or trade in society, especially by the urgent need to address the maelstrom of information that surrounds us with conceptual, technical and ethical tools.

The evolution of Internet from 1990 to the present, the emergence of social networks, the migration of a large part of academic-scientific activities to the digital world and the decrease in the costs of acquiring computer resources and services (Griffiths et al., 2016; Suber, 2012) have set an agenda that cannot be rejected by professionals who are directly or indirectly linked to the world of data and information. The current dilemma is not only in the amount of data, but in what to do with all of it; how to manage large volumes of structured, semi-structured and unstructured digital information, generated by mobile devices, sensors, computer applications, among others, and, created by individuals, agencies and/or public and private companies in all areas of society.

Thus, due to the need to collect, analyze and use data, the Big Data (BD) appears, which is characterized as the technology that allows processing large amounts of data in a short time (Cf. Rajaraman & Ullman, 2011), since the processing and subsequent analysis of data and/or information, in many cases, must be done in real time to influence timely decision making. The typical characterization of a Big Data problem is whether it

complies with: a large volume (large data collections), with a variety of sources both structured and unstructured (absence of structure) and with speed in relation to the generation, access and analysis of the data to be exploited, in addition to being able to give veracity to the information and value to the data (Agarwal et al., 2011; Tascón, 2013; Yu & Wang, 2015).

However, how data collection, analysis and use should be approached is also inherent to datification. It is understood that Big Data and datification are linked together. However, the latter has to do with the action of converting and measuring information, a process or an activity into data thanks to the existing technological infrastructure (Markus, 2017; Mayer-Schönberger & Cukier, 2013). In turn, datification is related to digitalization, however, Mayer and Cukier (2013) suggest that datification occurred before Information Technology, which allowed the emergence of digitalization. These authors explain that datification refers to data transformed, through analysis and reorganization, into information that can be used in any area of knowledge or discipline. In contrast, digitalization (Mayer-Schönberger & Cukier, 2013) is the process by which analog information is converted into digital (binary codes of zeros and ones) so that it is readable and processed by a computer. In summary, with datification the data can be quantified so that they can be tabulated and analyzed, then stored in different formats in order to apply Big Data (Marín & Lisbona, 2018).

Retrieval, transformation and visualization can be thought of as the processes of datification. Thus, the retrieval process will consist of obtaining reliable data, either from specific media and/or infrastructure or through the application of patterns using existing algorithms and/or software. The data sources to perform the recovery can be very varied, but they will almost always be related to computer media. According to Soares (2012), data can be extracted for datification from: Web and social media (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, blogs, etc.), Machine-to-data (sensors, internet of things, smart phones), Big transaction data (health care claims, telecommunication records, utility billing records), Biometrics (biometric recognition or biometrics, refers to the automatic identification of a person based on their characteristics or anatomical or behavioral traits) and Human-generated data (human beings generate large amounts of data: call center agent notes, voice recordings, email, photos, videos, paper documents, surveys, electronic medical records).

On the other hand, the transformation process aims to cleanse and consolidate incoming data from different sources, so that you have accurate data that is correct, complete, consistent and unambiguous. And finally, the visualization process is understood as the monitoring of the data produced by the object of the datification (Lope Salvador et al., 2020; Markus, 2017; Mayer-Schönberger & Cukier, 2013).

The process of information and documentation provides a space of opportunity for professionals of information and documentation through the intervention of computer techniques and theories that should be known or promoted in work with computer scientists. For example, these processes have a great similarity with the pattern of software architecture known as ETL (extraction, transformation and load) used for data integration in Computer Science (expand in Ashima et al., 2015). This pattern consists of three consecutive functional stages: the extraction of data from different sources, the transformations required by the heterogeneity of the information through rules, and the final loading into a database system (Awad et al., 2011; El-Sappagh et al., 2011; Texier et al., 2017). This architecture is used to unify information in business intelligence processes that lead to decision making.

Therefore, a relationship can be established between part of the ETL processes and the datification, but taking out the loading phase, since loading would be a computer process related to the handling of different database paradigms that respect criteria such as unique values, referential integrity, mandatory fields and value range checks (Texier et al., 2017).

Without a doubt, the area of discipline that has the most opportunities for these datification processes is that of the Library and Information Sciences, because they are the ones called upon to implement the processes in accordance with the skills developed in academic training and work experience.

2. Reflection

After understanding the concept of datification, it can be stated that computer scientists have developed a set of skills necessary to understand an ETL process similar to datification, but with a weakness in the area of data cataloguing. Several authors confirm (e.g., Chowdhury & Chowdhury, 1999; Liew, 2009; Nguyen & Chowdhury, 2013; Pomerantz et al., 2006; Texier et al., 2012) the relationship between professionals in the LIS domain and professionals in the computer sciences, taking into account the paradigmatic changes in data/information acquisition and access to knowledge. It is also shown by the various topics and papers presented at conferences and journals in the area: Joint Conference on Digital Libraries (JCDL); Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries (TPDL); the International Conference on Asian Digital Libraries (ICADL); and the IEEE Technical Committee on Digital Libraries (TCDL). Some topics presented: digitization, storage and exchange; digital objects, composition and packages; metadata, cataloguing, author management; repositories, archives; interoperability, mediators; search services, linking, browsing; natural language processing; data integrity, preservation; artificial intelligence.

On the other hand, Morato et al. (2016) affirm the low labor demand for professionals in Information Sciences and Documentary Sciences despite the increase in technological specialization. The authors predict an increase in the demand and need for technological/computer skills in the LIS domain. This translates into an opportunity because it makes visible the importance of developing the necessary competences for the datification that has been described in the LIS professional profiles. Other authors, mainly Fox (2019), have proposed the development of a DL Curriculum to strengthen the development of LIS competences and, therefore, the datification processes (Franks, 2014; ILS, 2013; Oh et al., 2016; Pomerantz et al., 2006; Shuva & Audunson, 2014; Tammaro, 2013; Texier et al., 2016; Texier & Zambrano, 2019). This DL Curriculum proposes training in computer skills to address different topics developed in LIS domain programs. It is highlighted that the DL Curriculum for LIS professionals can be directed through postgraduate academic programs, while for Computer Science professionals it can be incorporated in elective subjects at the end of their careers (Texier et al., 2016; Texier & Zambrano, 2019).

The LIS professionals, by actively participating in the retrieval, transformation and visualization of existing data, will allow the improvement of the reporting processes and will obtain as a result data quality that will lead to more precise searches available to a more varied audience. An ideal of data quality would be the European Union's guide of principles, known as FAIR Data (European Commission, 2018) that although it is oriented to scientific data can be used to consider what data quality in any discipline is. The development of this FAIR guide was achieved with the support of various sectors interested (academia, industry, funding bodies, academic publishers, governments) in providing data that computers (or rather algorithms) can find, access, interoperate and reuse without any or minimal human intervention.

In other words, the principles refer to Findable the large amount of data can be found through the metadata that identifies, describes and locates it. Accessible because large volumes of data can be retrieved using standardized communication protocols, and the metadatas are persistent even when the data is no longer available. Interoperable because the multitude of data from this era must be able to be exchanged with at least two systems or software components. Reusable because all recovered and transformed data can be reused because its origin and the conditions of its reuse are known (European Commission, 2018; Tanhua et al., 2019).

Having a large amount of reliable data or quality data becomes a juncture that information professionals could take advantage of in what is currently known as information and/or digital literacy. With the leverage of current technological advances, new forms of relationships between people have been promoted and many daily processes have changed, which are increasingly controlled by technological devices (Pino, 2010). Therefore, through literacy, training processes are democratized and social and labor inclusion and an improvement in the quality of life are achieved (Ortega, 2009). In this search for new ways of approaching and appropriating information technologies, universities play a fundamental role because they serve as a space for the creation of supports (software, hardware), education, research (on the functioning of these supports and how to use them) and the linkage (extension) with the community and other sectors of society, as well as promoting interdisciplinarity through collaboration in work teams led by librarians, archivists and/or documentalists, with tasks typical of their knowledge: retrieval, transformation, data preservation and construction of virtual communities.

Another great opportunity to take into account in the processes of datification in the "Information Era" has to do with the use of technological developments and implementations, which Vidal et al. (2019) propose as disruptive changes that cannot be ignored, among them, cloud services where data can be retrieved, processed and visualized with computer technologies available on the Internet (not installed on a local computer); blockchains (improve data management, thanks to the tracking of the processes of the retrieved and/or created data); computational linguistics that enables computers to process and understand natural language (expand on Vallez & Pedraza, 2007); Machine learning by searching for patterns within a large amount of data through high-performance algorithms and computer processing; the semantic web so that search engines can understand data and information, i.e., published data (datified) can be readable (interoperable) by computers through their semantic and ontological metadata; MOOCs: there is an opportunity (little offer) for the LIS discipline because they are open and massive courses (expand in Zade & Babare, 2020); open science because of the openness of the whole research process and the generation of products (Alonso-Arévalo & Lopes, 2019); and, the bibliographic databases of free access, for example: Lens.org, the new Microsoft Academic, Google Scholar, Dimensions, 1findr.

Lope Salvador et al. (2020) point out that the opportunities of a new digital paradigm for information professionals are in the alliance between Data Science and Neuroscience providing ways to integrate meaning and subjectivity in Science, therefore, they mention the conjunction of computational linguistics and machine learning. This idea, together with the others that have been outlined, identify, in some way, many of the needs for knowledge and technological skills (closely related to the processes of datification) that are favoring the labor insertion of professionals in the LIS domain and that are in line with the portals of job offers such as Laboris.net and LinkedIn, where such needs indicate that professionals must adapt to new contexts in order to provide users with accessible, relevant and quality data and information, which gradually changes the roles of jobs (Méndez & van Hooland, 2009; Morato et al, 2016).

3. Conclusions

The great challenge for the domain of Library and Information Sciences before the datification processes is to be able to rethink the need to improve day after day and to contribute from another place for all disciplines. In this way, current and future professionals will be able to develop the necessary competences to be present in different phases of datification (searches, primary data from any research, transformation, visualization) and to contribute with the knowledge, skills and attitudes acquired in other disciplinary fields.

This challenge must obviously be accompanied and thought from an interdisciplinary perspective, since we are facing an increasingly complex society and it is affected by events that cannot be addressed from a single

disciplinary perspective. It is emphasized that training (development of competences) must be oriented to basic knowledge and not to the updating of software tools. In such a way that the LIS professionals will be able to keep up to date with courses or workshops on computer tools and techniques thinking about disruptive changes. Therefore, the LIS domain will have to adapt to new contexts in order to provide the user with accessible, relevant and quality information.

To conclude, it is a priority to think of innovative teaching and training proposals, for example, the DL Curriculum that will allow the public's perception of the profile of LIS professionals to be modified, in order to understand that they can help other disciplines in the process of certification, but taking into account the component of globalization, that is, collaboration between different LIS faculties and departments, between academics, between libraries, between employees, all of these in different parts of the world, maximizing resources, experience and facilities (cf. with Rehman, 2008). In today's world, there is nothing but being open, creative, innovative and entrepreneurial. A recent study (Xue et al., 2019) shows the commitment to transform LIS education in the two largest countries in the world, China and the United States, which also have a huge territorial extension that makes the commitment even more difficult. The authors identify and discuss four types of challenges in LIS education by analyzing quantitatively and qualitatively the data collected from these countries China and the United States: 1) identity and accreditation, 2) survival and prosperity, 3) curriculum updating and improvement, and 4) course delivery format and content.

In short, the generation of data by each user today is enormous and the important thing is not to get tired of datifying for datifying's sake, but to ask the right question. The goal is to analyze before collecting data and this is achieved with education and not by a stroke of luck or by simply handling a tool. Without a doubt, the training of information and documentation professionals requires changes that transcend data and impact decision making that allow us to understand that a data is resignified with the use and impact it produces in others. The challenge, without a doubt, is to provide innovative and quality training that takes advantage of the opportunities this hyper-informed historical moment offers us.

4. References

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